

Solid state conductance in sucrose and its allied crystalline products

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The dc electrical conductivity of AnalaR reagent sucrose (ARS), refined sugar (RS), beet sugar (BS) and plantation white sugar (PWS) across the temperature range of 305–350 K has been measured *in vacuo* employing an abonite conductivity cell of the configuration Cu/pellet/Cu. The aforesaid crystals have measurable electronic conductivities, with temperature dependence similar to that of conventional semiconductors. The absolute values of the conductivity is several orders of magnitude lower than in most semiconductors, and is greater for the larger molecular species. As a group they may be classified as poor insulator or semiconductor, according to preference. The observed electrical conductivity, very likely, has its origin the inclusion or adsorption of impurities (ash and non-sugars) in the $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$ crystal. Characteristic activation energies ranging from 0.27 to 0.35 eV suggest that there is a protonic conduction mechanism in the sucrose which is attributed to the protons of hydrogen bond network present in the sucrose crystal. A comparative study with the conductivity of octamethyl sucrose where there is no hydrogen bonds brings considerable added assurance to both technique employed as well as endorsing the validity of the results in the sense that octa-methyl sucrose crystals have no electrical conductivity which confirms the participation of hydrogen bond as charge carrier which is thought to be responsible for the observed conductivity.

In continuation of our work on solid phase conductivity of sugar¹, in the present one we have initiated to quantify the electrical conductivity of sucrose crystal as a representative selection of carbohydrates and to evaluate its correlation with sugar quality. The main objective was to obtain fundamental data on the electronic properties of solid crystalline sucrose : a key compound in the metabolism of living organisms, and a major commercial product. Therefore, electronic properties of a wide variety of sugar and its allied crystalline products were probed, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Such investigations will be of significant help in understanding and solving problems related to sugar quality and its storage and more fundamental scientific issues such as determining the basic mechanism of charge transport in the crystals.

Results and discussion

Polarization behaviour :

A constant voltage at constant contact pressure was applied to the cell configuration Cu/sucrose/Cu across the temperature range of 305–350 K and polarization current (PC) was followed as a function of time. Typical PC are shown in Fig. 1 which illustrate that initial PC was significantly higher which decreases to a constant value after 20 min. On

reversal of polarity it was observed that PC was instantaneously increases to initial state. PC was found to increase with increase in temperature.

The specific conductivity versus temperature plots for the compounds under study shown in Fig. 2 clearly illustrate their biphasic nature. This may be due to different factors such as change in crystal form at higher temperature or change in the charge carriers from one mechanism to other or by occurrence of side by side mechanism of two different charge carriers. The observed specific conductivity's for

Fig. 1. Polarization curve for the cell : Cu/sucrose/Cu.

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Fig. 2. Specific conductivity versus temperature plots for different sugar crystals.

ARS, RS, BS and PWS at 305 K were 1.34×10^{-9} , 1.46×10^{-9} , 2.01×10^{-9} and $2.10 \times 10^{-9} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The order of magnitude of conductivity for all the sugar crystals was the same across the temperature range tested (305–350 K), and conductivity of all the sugars increased with increasing temperature. Thus, conductivity was much higher at 338 and 350 K than at 305, 314 or 323 K. The specific conductivity of PWS at 305 K was found to be $2.10 \times 10^{-9} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which increased by factors of two and four at 323 and 350 K, respectively. Similar behaviour was also observed for beet sugar crystals. Representative data are shown in Table 1. It is generally expected that at higher temperature and higher concentration of impurities, the conductance of the pellets are higher, consequently, the current flow in the circuit will be higher due to which P.D. across the standard resistance is expected to increase. Results consistent with this sequence of events were found in these experiments. The higher observed conductivity's for plantation white sugar and beet sugar at all temperatures seem to be attributable to their higher concentration of impurities (ash and non-sugars) compared to AnalaR sample of sucrose and refined sugar crystal. The higher conductivity's for PWS and BS, very likely have their ori-

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots for different sugar crystals.

gin in the inclusion or adsorption of impurities during their processing.

Applying the Arrhenius equation to the conductivity data, characteristic activation energies can be derived for each sample in order to understand the conduction mechanism in the sucrose. The Arrhenius plots, shown in Fig. 3, are reasonably linear, and suggest activation energies of 0.35, 0.34, 0.29 and 0.27 eV for ARS, RS, BS and PWS, respectively. The activation energies seem to suggest that there is a protonic conduction mechanism in the $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}$ and is attributed to the protons of

sucrose crystal. There are several considerations which strongly favour proton of hydrogen bond network as charge carriers. The fact that when hydrogen-bonded protons can take part in charge transport in ice, proteins, and resins², then there is no reason why this system should not be involved in transporting charge in the sucrose crystal which is also a good candidate of hydrogen bonding or where the existence of HB are well understood. A very interesting elucidation can be had from the neutron diffraction structure⁵ of sucrose which revealed two strong intramolecular hydrogen bonds ($\text{O}-2^{\text{g}} \cdots \text{HO}-1^{\text{f}}$, $\text{O}-5^{\text{g}} \cdots \text{HO} \cdots 6^{\text{f}}$) which serve

Table 1. Electrical conductivity of sucrose and its allied crystalline products at different temperature

Sample	Specific conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)					Activation energy (eV)
	305 K	314 K	323 K	338 K	350 K	
ARS	1.34×10^{-9}	1.99×10^{-9}	3.10×10^{-9}	5.09×10^{-9}	7.41×10^{-9}	0.35
RS	1.46×10^{-9}	2.10×10^{-9}	3.39×10^{-9}	5.41×10^{-9}	7.68×10^{-9}	0.34
BS	2.01×10^{-9}	2.98×10^{-9}	4.05×10^{-9}	6.15×10^{-9}	7.85×10^{-9}	0.29
PWS	2.10×10^{-9}	3.00×10^{-9}	4.17×10^{-9}	6.58×10^{-9}	8.04×10^{-9}	0.27

to hold the molecule in a well ordered, rigid conformation in which two rings are approximately at right angles and in which the pyranosyl residue adopts a 4C_1 conformation and the furanoside ring a 3T_4 twist. Apart from HO-4, all the -OH groups are intermolecularly hydrogen bonded. A comparative study with the conductivity of octa-methyl sucrose where there is no hydrogen bonds has revealed that octa-methyl sucrose crystals have no electrical conductivity which confirms the participation of hydrogen bond as charge carrier which is thought to be responsible for the observed conductivity. A comparative study with the sugar alcohols³ which have infinite chains of -O-H...O-H...O-H- bonds, as in ice would provide an additional evidence of hydrogen bond network as charge carriers in $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$. Moreover, if the conductance were due to proton shifts in this network⁴, replacement of hydrogen by deuterium should exert a marked lowering in the observed conductance. However, this is beyond the scope of the present investigation. This work has been undertaken in a separate research project. Further work is the progress on the effects of isotopic substitution of hydrogen by deuterium.

Conclusions :

The electrical conductivity measurement of various crystalline sugars led to the following important conclusions;

- (1) The observed specific conductivity's suggest that conductivity measurement of sugars in solid phase may be an important means of estimating of sugar quality, since the less pure sugars had higher conductivity.
- (2) The electrical conductance of the different sugars are low but quite definite and reproducible. The temperature dependence of the conductivity showed the $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$ to be a semiconductor.
- (3) The characteristic activation energies ranging from 0.27 to 0.35 eV, suggested a protonic conduction mechanism attributable to hydrogen bond network present in the crystal. A comparative study with the conductivity of octa-methyl sucrose where there is no hydrogen bonds has revealed that octa-methyl sucrose crystals have no electrical conductivity which confirms the participation of hydrogen bond as charge carrier which is thought to be responsible for the observed conductivity, and
- (4) Electrical conductivity measurement of a wide variety of sugar and its allied crystalline products could be made qualitative as well as quantitative, and such investigations could help in understanding and solving problems related to sugar quality and its storage life.

Experimental

Sugar samples were collected from Bureau of Sugar Standards, National Sugar Institute, Kanpur (India). Fine powder was made by grinding weighed quantities of sugars and pellets of thickness and area of 2.5 mm and 0.515 cm² were made with these. The pellets were placed in an evacuated Abonite conductivity cell with copper electrodes (Fig. 4). The conductivity cell was kept inside the electrical furnace and surroundings was wrapped with asbestos and glass-

Fig. 4. Abonite conductivity cell.

wool in order to get moisture free environment. The temperature of the furnace and the samples were monitored with the help of a chromel-alumel thermocouple and also with an external thermometer. The calibration curve for the electrical furnace was drawn. Circuit diagram for conductivity measurements is as given in text books on the principle of a Wheatstone bridge⁶. After reaching thermal equilibrium which usually takes 4 h, Ohmic contact was ensured prior to any measurement. An external potential (9V)

was then applied from an external source, and a Kiethley 17 DDM multimeter was used to determine the p.d. across a standard resistance (2 M Ω) when pellets were in series with it. *Ceteris paribus*, the specific conductance of octamethyl sucrose was also investigated for comparison. Octamethyl sucrose was prepared by treatment of sucrose with dimethyl-sulphate in the presence of alkali employing the procedure described in the literature⁷.

The specific conductivity (σ) of the pellets is given by :

$$(\sigma) = C \times (l/A) \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1},$$

where l = thickness of the pellet = 0.25 cm, D = diameter of the pellet = 0.81 cm and A = cross-sectional area of the pellet

$$A = \pi r^2 = 3.14 \times (0.81/2)^2 \\ = 0.515 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$C = \text{conductance} = 1/R = I_{\text{sample}}/V_{\text{sample}}$$

Here, cell constant = $(1/A) = 0.25/0.515 = 0.485 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, current (I) = $V_R/R = V_R/2 \times 10^6$, voltage across the sample (V_{sample}) = $V_{\text{external}} - V_R$, current across the sample (I_{sample}) = $V_{\text{sample}}/R_{\text{sample}}$ and resistance of the sample (R_{sample}) = $V_{\text{sample}}/I_{\text{sample}}$.

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